

SHORT COMMUNICATIONS

Spergulagenic Acid : Its Conversion to 11-Deoxy Glycyrrhetic Acid

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We reported the isolation of a new sapogenin, spergulagenic acid¹, from *Mollugo spergula* in 1965 and elucidated its structure as 3 β -hydroxy-olean-12-en-28, 30-dioic acid (Ia)^{2,3}. Previously spergulagenic acid could be converted to oleanolic acid. It has now been possible to convert spergulagenic acid to 11-deoxy-18 β -glycyrrhetic acid (IIId) which further confirms the structure (Ia) previously assigned by us to spergulagenic acid.

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Spergulagenic acid (Ia) on refluxing with methanolic hydrogen chloride furnished a monomethyl ester (Ic), $C_{31}H_{48}O_5$, m.p. 276–80° (dec.), $[\alpha]_D^{32} + 113.3^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$). The C-30 carboxyl group in spergulagenic acid could be preferentially esterified under the above conditions yielding the monomethyl ester (Ic) because of the comparatively more hindered nature of the C-28 carboxyl group. The ester (Ic) was found to be different from the monomethyl ester (Id) m.p. 292–94°, $[\alpha]_D^{32} + 97^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$) prepared by partial saponification of dimethyl spergulagenate (Ib; *loc. cit.*). On heating with acetic anhydride and pyridine on steam-bath the monomethyl ester (Ic) furnished a mixed anhydride (Ie), $C_{35}H_{52}O_7$, m.p. 272–75°, $[\lambda]_{max}^{nu}$ 1800 cm^{-1} (anhydride), 1735 and 1240 cm^{-1} (acetoxo) and 1725 cm^{-1} (carbomethoxy)]. The above anhydride on refluxing with ethanol furnished a product (If), $C_{33}H_{50}O_6$, m.p. 231–33°, which showed no band for anhydride in the I.R. spectrum. Compound (If) was treated with thionyl chloride and the acid chloride (IIa) thus obtained was directly subjected to Rosenmund reduction yielding the aldehyde (IIb), m.p. 256–60°. This product on Wolff-Kishner reduction followed by diazomethane treatment gave a compound, $C_{31}H_{50}O_3$, m.p. 246–48°, identified as methyl ester (IIc) of 11-deoxo-18 β -glycyrrhetic acid by T.L.C. and mixed m.p. comparison. Methyl ester (IIc, m.p. 247–48°) of 11-deoxo-18 β -glycyrrhetic acid was prepared from methyl glycyrrhetate (III) by catalytic hydrogenation over Adams' catalyst in acetic acid medium⁴. Thus the conversion of spergulagenic acid to (IIc) leaves no doubt about the validity of the structure (Ia) previously assigned by us to spergulagenic acid.

In 1967 Savoir *et al.*⁵ reported the isolation of an acid called serjanic acid from a *Serjania* species in an amorphous state, but they did not mention its physical properties i.e., melting point, optical rotation etc. They, however, showed it to be a monomethyl ester of a triterpene dicarboxylic acid. They obtained the methyl ester of serjanic acid in crystalline state and suggested its structure as (Ib) which is same as assigned by us earlier to dimethyl spergulagenate (Ib). We believe that methyl serjaniate is identical with dimethyl spergulagenate. These authors isolated only 13 mg of amorphous serjanic acid and it is quite probable that the difference in physical constants of methyl serjaniate m.p. 226–29.5°, $[\alpha]_D + 78^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$) from those of dimethyl spergulagenate m.p. 235–37°, $[\alpha]_D^{32} + 101.3^\circ$ ($CHCl_3$) are due to the presence of impurities in methyl serjaniate. Serjanic acid should therefore be identical with one of the two monomethyl esters (Ic) and (Id) of spergulagenic acid reported by us. Unfortunately samples of serjanic acid and its methyl ester were not available for comparison purposes.

The authors express their sincere thanks to Prof. S. M. Sircar, Director and Prof. A. Sen, Head of the Department of Chemistry, Bose Institute, for their interest in the work.

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Received February 2, 1969.

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